

Multicultural Diversity and Theoretical Study

Dr. E. Gangadhar

Assistant Professor © Department of English
S.V.U College of Arts, S.V. University, Tirupati.
Andhra Pradesh -517502
drgangadhar18@gmail.com

Abstract

The concept of intercultural diversity encompasses all measures that address social responses to current difficulties, whether at the national or organizational level. Multiculturalism and diversity encompass a wide range of elements, including gender, race/ethnicity, language, sexual orientation, age, spiritual orientation, physical ability, knowledge, skills, socioeconomic level, geographical location, and others. This research paper will therefore strive to review the literature on numerous elements of intercultural diversity. These include the definition of multicultural diversity, a brief theoretical framework of diversity, the aspects of multicultural diversity, the Impacts of Multicultural Diversity on Organizational Work Groups, key factors that are important in determining how successful individuals will be in interacting with a changing society, and finally, the challenges involved when working in a multicultural organization. Power dynamics within groups, merging diversity of opinion and approaches, real and perceived tokenism, the challenge of holding all individuals throughout the organization accountable for achieving a positive multicultural environment, and communication challenges within a multicultural organization were among the issues discussed.

Keywords: Multiculturalism, diversity, organizational challenges, spiritual orientation, physical ability, and geographical location.

Literature Review

Multiculturalism and diversity are terms used to describe actions taken by society in response to issues that people are accustomed to disregarding. The diversity notion focuses on distinctions, whereas multiculturalism deals with elements of multiple cultures. Religion, fair employment opportunity, affirmative action, social-economic position, culture and ethnicity, and other factors all contribute to the concept of diversity. Multiculturalism, on the other hand, is concerned with the interactions that exist between groups that share a socio-cultural legacy, such as religion, history, and lineage. Individuals' multicultural abilities include being knowledgeable about their cultural differences, cognizant of their attitudes and views, and skilled at dealing with diverse groups.

Received: 22 March. 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

Multicultural awareness is essential for any organizational setting because it demands individuals to be aware of the values, assumptions, and prejudices that are embedded in their culture, experiences, heritage, and sociopolitical environment (Sue, 2006). As a result, comprehending multiculturalism and diversity requires consideration of gender, race/ethnicity, language, sexual orientation, age, spiritual orientation, physical ability, knowledge, skills, socioeconomic level, geographical location, and a variety of other characteristics. Societies around the world vary greatly in all respects. As a result, multicultural abilities are essential for the growth and prosperity of communities and companies

Multicultural competences address concerns of awareness, knowledge, and skills (Sisaye, 2005). Multiculturalism teaches people that, as cultural beings, they have attitudes and beliefs that shape how they view and interact with people from various ethnic and racial backgrounds. Individuals face a lifetime of multicultural learning since their life experiences differ from those of others. Individuals must be mindful of their values, preconceptions, and biases based on their culture, experiences, sociopolitical context, heritage, and so on. It also helps people realize how their cultural backgrounds affect their attitudes, behavior, preconceptions, and preconceived notions (Halverson, 2008).

In the absence of this self-awareness, they will struggle to comprehend other people. They must comprehend the distinctions that might exist between them and those from other cultures as well as their own cultural backgrounds. People must always be learning about different cultures in order to develop new talents. Today's top companies have implemented diversity training initiatives that work. Initiatives for cultural understanding may also be a part of these diversity training programs (Connerley, 2005).

People working in organizational settings must become knowledgeable about multiculturalism. They must so acquire knowledge and actively seek out information about various people's cultures, viewpoints, and experiences. They must also understand other varied groups' values, beliefs, family dynamics, histories, and heritages. However, in applied contexts like therapeutic settings, multicultural abilities are essential (Parakh, 2000).

Received: 22 March, 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

Diversity of theories

Capozza (2000) defined variety as a mixture of individuals within the same social system who belong to different groups. The ideas behind diversity are explained by a number of theoretical frameworks. The Social Identity Theory (SIT) and Embedded Inter-Group Relations theory are covered in this essay. Among the well-known inter-group theories that help us understand group identities in organizations is the social identity theory.

This idea looks at organizational diversity. According to Sue (2006), a cognitive theory, people have a tendency to categorize themselves and other people into social classes, and these classifications have a significant impact on how people interact. People can learn about the effects of diversity in a broad sense through social identity; the topic of the particular content of socially defined classes is not addressed, though.

Furthermore, it does not address organizational structures or systems. It also fails to account for the significant importance of race, gender, class, and sexual orientation, all of which are deeply ingrained in American and other countries' history and social experience. This theory assumes that groupings defined by socially significant distinctions will have similar impacts to nominally established groups (McRae, 2009).

McRae (2009) defines Embedded Inter-group Relations framework as an important framework for explaining multicultural diversity notions. The theory was designed for organizations that combine identity group membership with group membership derived from organizational classification. It proposes the existence of two types of groups within organizations: identity groups, which have some common biological elements such as sex, equivalent historical experiences, are subjected to similar social forces, and have relatively consonant world views; and organizational groups, which have common organizational positions and are involved in equivalent work experiences, resulting in relatively consonant worldviews. While physical participation in identity groups is limited, members may feel more or less identified with their respective identity groups (Haslam, S.).(2003)

Received: 22 March, 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

Despite the fact that identification group membership comes before organizational group membership, the two are typically closely intertwined. For example, certain organizational groupings are dominated by members of specific identification groups. According to Haslam (2003), older white males make up the majority of executive management in US firms. According to Embedded Inter-Group Relations Theory, individuals and organizations are continually seeking to manage possible conflicts that arise at the intersection of identity groups and organizational group membership. Tension management is influenced by a variety of elements, the most important of which is how groups are integrated into the organization (McRae, 2009)

Aspects of Multicultural Diversity.

We live in a great world full with diverse people and civilizations. One culture cannot be deemed better or inferior to another. In educational institutions, for example, educators must strive to see people from different cultures through their eyes rather than ours. This is significant because it fosters educational environments that respect and appreciate many cultures, nationalities, and races.

Teachers and students may have attitudes that are ethnocentric, racist, or stereotypical. These attitudes are major hurdles to identifying sensitivity to different cultures and ethnic groups (Albrecht, 2001). Ethnocentricity is the notion that one's own culture or ethnic group is superior to others, or the refusal to acknowledge the existence or validity of other cultural groups and their rituals, values, beliefs, and conventions (Banks, 2009).

Racism refers to an attitude that regards particular cultural or ethnic groups as fundamentally inferior to others and thus vulnerable to exploitation, discrimination, and other forms of mistreatment. Stereotypes are the conscious or unconscious attribution of exaggerated and/or oversimplified beliefs, attitudes, or judgments about individuals of a specific ethnic or cultural group. Prejudice, on the other hand, is a negative attitude toward a specific group formed by comparison with the individual's own group as a positive reference point (Park-Brown, 2003).

Received: 22 March, 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

Teachers must ensure that personal attitudes, stereotypes, and prejudices do not influence their instruction. For example, a teacher who was raised in one cultural group and may have stereotypes or prejudices against other cultural groups must overcome these assumptions and prejudices in order to successfully educate students from that cultural group. Stereotypes and prejudices are not limited to ethnic or cultural groups; they may also apply to the physically handicapped, the elderly, certain sorts of persons, and others (Banks, 2009).

Educators can increase ethnic and cultural sensitivity in a variety of ways. They should strive to demonstrate suitable personal abilities, such as displaying respect, concern, warmth, care, and honesty to people from all cultural or ethnic backgrounds. In addition, cross-cultural understanding must be fostered in the communities where teachers work and reside. They should also attempt to recognize culturally determined opinions and behavioral standards, such as specific knowledge and respect for differences. In addition to building personal cross-cultural awareness among cultural or ethnic groups, educators should prioritize cross-cultural competency in the curriculum for pupils (Park-Brown, 2003).

It is also critical for educators to pay particular attention to culturally or ethnically appropriate learning and problem-solving strategies. This should include identifying a number of tactics and ways for completing jobs efficiently. In fact, they should promote a range of approaches. Finally, they should recognize that the appropriate style, manner, and topic of communication for a specific cultural group aids in learning. This includes using culturally or ethnically desired nonverbal abilities like eye contact, body language, and physical proximity (Page, 2003).

The Impacts of Multicultural Diversity on Directorial Work Groups

According to research on multicultural organizational work groups, cultural diversity has a good and bad impact on these groups. This study illustrates that, while cultural diversity may eventually result in increased efficiency and production, multicultural workgroups must first overcome the challenges that diversity introduces to the group process. Multicultural workgroups sometimes struggle to achieve the ideal work process due to communication breakdowns,

Received: 22 March, 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

continual conflicts on expectations, and attitude issues such as mistrust, dislikes, and a lack of cohesion (Banks, 2009).

Such challenges tend to offset the good influence of diversity on multicultural groups. The efficacy and effectiveness of culturally diverse groups are closely related to their ability to overcome such issues. The difference in interactions between culturally diverse and culturally homogeneous groups is understood to some extent. However, research on the impact of these obstacles on the decision-making and productivity of culturally varied individuals remains limited. Group interaction with culturally heterogeneous behaviors differs significantly from those of culturally homogeneous groups in three dimensions: expectations and integration, cohesion, fight and flight (Chmiel 2000).

To avoid economic stagnation, organizations must recognize these difficulties and implement the necessary policies. Today, the rise and influence of global trading regions have begun to outweigh national interests. Individuals in business and education will continue to face new obstacles as diversity grows. Diversity in the workforce is covered, as are investments, particularly in the United States and around the world. It is critical to identify and respond to emerging difficulties at all levels before they constitute a permanent risk to nations' economic stability (Halverson, 2008).

Today, the modern global economy is spread across multiple countries and cities. A new global economy is made up of a network of relationships connected by electronic communication via computers, phones, TV, fax, electronic mail, satellite, and people. For example, automotive parts are manufactured in many nations and shipped to central assembly plants. Furthermore, America exports products for manufacture under foreign nameplates as well as its own brand. All of this implies a diversity of ownership, production, consumers, capital, and staff. Today, the most significant problem that business and education executives face is managing expanding diversity in a global economic environment (Chmiel, 2000).

Received: 22 March, 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

Challenges of Working in a Multicultural Organization.

Organizational change can take a long time to implement, and numerous challenges may occur along the way. Among the most difficult challenges that organizations encounter as they attempt to implement change may include managing the reaction of staff members of the dominant culture, who may wish to maintain the status quo; synthesizing diversity of opinions from individuals and applying them as a basis for concluding meaningful agreements on issues; and avoiding real or perceived tokenism and quota systems that can assist organizations in achieving goals but can be destructive .

According to Chmiel (2000), organizational distinctions stem from their ability to capitalize on the different qualities of a multicultural workforce and use these differences to create a richer, more productive work environment. Many organizations and entities struggle to overcome entrenched attitudes and behaviors. In some rigid firms, legislative criteria for workforce composition are respected, but nothing more is done to recruit or retain a multicultural staff. Routines and hiring practices within firms remain unchanged for decades (Ferreira, 2009). Other organizations that are marginally more interested in diversity actively hire and employ people from diverse backgrounds in the organization's everyday procedures and routines, but their skills and abilities are not fully utilized. Few firms, however, embrace the concept of multiculturalism and use their workforce's variety to create a nonconforming, creative, and dynamic atmosphere.

These are places in which people's differences are not just tolerated, but actively promoted. Working in a multicultural setting presents numerous obstacles, as do the diverse demographics and dynamics of the workplace. However, common challenges include fluctuating power dynamics, combining diverse opinions and approaches, tokenism, reality or perception, holding people throughout the organization accountable for creating a positive multicultural environment, and communicating with the multicultural organization (Ferreira, 2009).

Received: 22 March, 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

Difficulties of Communicating into Multicultural Organisations

Managing cultural diversity is a practical skill that aims to change organizational culture. It is an organizational development effort centered on intergroup prejudices (Gallos, 2006). It is obvious that what individuals of an organization choose to do with diversity has a direct impact on the organization; even if this entails changing prevalent attitudes and values regarding differences, the primary difficulty is communication effectiveness. Communication that affirms organizational members' identities and relationships while supporting attainment of their separate goals is particularly important in multicultural work situations (Banks, 2000).

Conclusion

To summarize, all nations have embraced multiculturalism. Any nation's success at all levels is determined on the strategies it implements to manage diversity in its distinct multicultural realms (Chmiel 2000). They must also address the issues that multicultural societal diversity institutions face, such as the national civil service and private organizations. These issues are genuine and must be addressed if authorities are to properly run society's life and be entities in which people trust and have confidence. This research examined the literature on the major concepts of intercultural diversity.

Reference List

- Albrecht, M. (2001). *International HRM*. New York: Wiley & Sons.
- Banks, S. (2000). *Multicultural Public Relations*. New York: Wiley and Sons.
- Connerley, M., & Pedersen, P. (2005). *Leadership in a Diverse Multicultural Environment*. California: SAGE.
- Halverson, C., & Tirmizi, A. (2008). *Effective Multicultural Team*. New York: Springer.
- Haslam, S. (2003). *Social Identity at Work*. New York: Taylor and Francis.
- McRae, M., & Short, E. (2009). *Racial and Cultural Dynamics in Group and Organizations*. California: SAGE.